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Glossary

GWP	Global Warming Potential
LULUCF	Land-use, land-use cover and forestry
ECEMF	European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum
CCG	Carbon capture and sequestration (storage)
ETS	Emissions Trading Scheme
ESR	
GHG	Green-house gas
IAMC	Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium

Background

Model Diagnostic exercises aim to characterize, compare and classify the behaviour of models for climate policy analysis. The experimental setup is dedicated to generating model output that can be used to estimate a set of diagnostic indicators of model response to carbon pricing policies. The ultimate goal is to better understand differences in model behaviour, enable fingerprinting of model responses, and classify models along with their fingerprints. The ECEMF T1.1 diagnostic study protocol builds on the diagnostics exercise protocol from the ADVANCE project (December 2014) and NAVIGATE project (March 2020), see study results (Harmsen et al., 2021): <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abf964>. The diagnostic indicators defined here will be henceforth referred to as the *Harmsen indicators*.

Participation opportunities

The diagnostic scenarios described here are currently run by project members of the EU Horizon project ECEMF. We invite modelling teams that are not part of the ECEMF project to contribute to a second round of the diagnostic scenario exercise that will start end of 2022.

If you are interested in contributing, please contact us at info@ecemf.eu.

New diagnostic scenarios in the ECEMF project

The purpose of the ECEMF diagnostic exercise is to develop a set of diagnostic scenarios from all contributing models. These diagnostics should:

1. Deliver plausible ranges for a number of variables required by other WPs as boundary conditions. These include CO₂ prices, primary energy prices, final energy demand by sector, CO₂ emissions/budgets across sectors, technology costs & deployment.
2. Identify model-specific challenges and potential weaknesses in the representation of climate-neutral scenarios. These weaknesses should be addressed during the course of the project.
3. Enhance model typology, interpretation, and transparency.

In ECEMF, the ADVANCE/NAVIGATE diagnostics protocol is complemented with additional scenario runs to further explore important aspects of the energy transformation, globally and in the EU, until 2050:

- Higher carbon price diagnostic scenarios, to get a better understanding of the near-term changes under high policy stringency, including regional and sectoral emission abatement costs and limits.
- Net zero greenhouse gas emissions for the EU in 2050, aimed at understanding the requirements and transformations needed to implement the climate neutrality policy goal. This will be based on models' default pathways to reach net-zero emissions in 2050.
- Technology constraints, where the use of unproven or controversial technologies are limited. These scenarios are aimed at identifying the role of these technologies in climate change mitigation pathways and provide alternative pathways where these technologies are not available.

Paradigm shift scenarios test whether the model is able to reasonably represent the structural shifts that are currently proposed by many bottom-up energy system models. These scenarios will show if a model is able to represent deep changes that may potentially happen (deep electrification, high use of renewable energy sources, strong scale-up of hydrogen) and still show reasonable behaviours and costs. How exactly the model is pushed into these paradigm shifts has still to be determined and will likely be different for different model types (optimization, simulation, etc.)

Upload Specification

Overview and priorities

The diagnostic scenario setup consists of a total of 12 scenarios, which are explained in the section on Scenarios and listed in Table 1 of ECEMF. (2022). Model Comparison Protocol (2.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6782403>

References

Koch, Johannes, and Marian Leimbach. 2022. 'Update of Ssp GDP Projections: Capturing Recent Changes in National Accounting, PPP Conversion and Covid 19 Impacts'. SSRN Scholarly Paper. Rochester, NY. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4011838>.

Annex 1 – Scenario details. They are constructed with the purpose of providing boundary conditions for the more detailed sectoral models used in ECEMF as well as allowing the academic community to conduct model diagnostics. They are explicitly not intended to provide policy analysis, but to test model dynamics under (partially extreme) inputs. We split the output that is to be uploaded into different priority levels. Teams should focus on first getting priority 1 (prio1) variables uploaded correctly, and in a second step add priority 2 (prio2) variables. Priority 3 (prio3) variables are nice to have, but not mandatory.

Scenario priorities

All scenarios described in Table 1 should be run by each model (except for the scenarios that do not make sense for purely supply-side models). We distinguish two types of scenarios: those with *Priority Level 1*, which mostly focus on pricing and peak budget assumptions, allowing to identify the sensitivity of model with respect to carbon pricing, and those with *Priority Level 2*, which vary more specific aspects of the energy system such as limiting potentials for biomass and CCS.

Naming convention of scenarios

The IIASA scenario explorer only accepts scenarios with the correct naming. We will use the naming *exactly* as they are defined in Table 1 (second column) below, including hyphens and capital characters (note: the scenario database is case-sensitive, incorrect capitalization or hyphenation leads to problems).

Time horizon and carbon pricing

The minimal requirements are the years 2020, 2030 and 2050. These years are all used in the calculation of the Harmsen indicators, using 2020 as a base year, required when calculating the Transformation Index and the Fossil Fuel Reduction. For better temporal resolution, it would be better to have all years between 2010-2100 at 5-year increments. We realize that 2020 may not be representative in terms of multi-annual trends in energy systems due to the COVID-19 crisis. For some models, this may create complications where the COVID-19 crisis determines much of the output later. Therefore, we ask modelling teams to adjust the year 2020 accordingly, for example by creating counterfactual 2020 comparison values by averaging the period 2018-2022. For models that use historic GDP or energy use as drivers, one might (a) not use actual 2020 values, but averaged values as input (advised if possible), or (b) use actual 2020 values, but do averaging ex-post. We do require suitable documentation of these decisions per model in time, for which details will follow. Observed historical data may be available on the IIASA database later, which may be used for this purpose.

In most of the scenarios, carbon price evolutions are prescribed per year. If carbon price levels exceed the domain of applicability of a given model, the modelling team should fix the carbon price at the highest level the model can run in the years after this level was reached. The naming of the carbon price scenario is specified in 2010 US dollars to make the scenarios directly comparable to the older ADVANCE diagnostic scenario runs, but conversion factors to go to different years or to Euro are given in Annex 2 – Currency conversions.

Regions

For initial analyses, we require all models to provide output on the level of **EU27 & UK** as it has the smallest mismatch to the regional mapping of the contributing models. However, for later policy-relevant analyses, **EU27** should be our goal, and more detailed analyses (also in other work packages) additionally require country-specific output on Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, The Netherlands, Poland and Sweden. Given model possibilities, output on the World level is a good addition, as well.

Because of differences in regional definitions and resolutions, the aggregation of regions and countries (e.g., to obtain EU27 & UK) may need to be tailored to each model. There are two alternative ways to currently do so:

1. Locally: create, before uploading, results containing the additional regional aggregations, e.g. EU27 and EU27&UK, derived from your model native regions and upload them to the database.
2. Automatic: the IIASA database can create additional region aggregations automatically based on your model's native regions. However, this requires adding model-specific support. Such aggregation is defined in the Open ENTRANCE Github repository. The modelling teams would need to follow two steps:
 - Add model native regions to:
https://github.com/openENTRANCE/openentrance/tree/main/definitions/region/model_native_regions
 - Create mapping file describing the conversion of these regions to database regions:
<https://github.com/openENTRANCE/openentrance/tree/main/mappings>

After both files are merged to the repository, whenever you upload new results in your native model regions, the IIASA server will create automatically the additional region aggregations necessary for the model comparisons.

Reporting Variables

The variable list is published in association with this protocol (on Zenodo), and linked on the ECEMF website.

Prio1 and Prio2 variables are required for each modelling team as they are associated with the basic model output necessary to have a general evaluation of the model ensembles, and those variables that are needed to generate the Harmsen indicators.

Additional, but not required variables are listed as prio3 variables: more detailed versions of prio1 and 2 variables which allow a more detailed sectoral analysis. This list may grow over time and will be finalized in Protocol v3.0.

Summarized, please focus on getting all must-have variables ready, with priority-1 variables being needed first and priority-2 variables later. Submit priority 3 variables if your model has this output as well.

Units and currencies

In line with using 2020 as a base year, we use **2020 euros** as the base currency for all monetary reporting variables, such as Policy Cost, GDP and Carbon price (even though in the scenario protocol we define the latter in USD as per Annex 1). Many models use US dollars. We ask you to report results in euros (2020) and use the conversion table between USD and EUR given in Annex 2 – Currency conversions, comprising Consumer Price Index (CPI) and exchange rates.

Emission sources

All budget and net-zero targets refer to emissions from “all anthropogenic sources” (i.e. both FFI and LULUCF) emissions. Similarly, carbon pricing is applied uniformly across all GHG emitting sectors. In the NZero scenarios, for models that do not include LULUCF emissions but cover all GHG, an EU “Fossil Fuel and Industry” emission constraint of 250 Mt CO₂-eq/yr should be applied. For a model that only covers CO₂ sources but includes LULUCF, the target should be minus 300 Mt CO₂ due to the assumption that non-CO₂ GHG will not be reduceable to zero (but rather stay around 300 MtCO₂-eq/yr). For a model that covers only CO₂ but no LULUCF the target should be minus ~50 MtCO₂. (values may be updated in the future once we have scenarios from more models covering the full system).

Emission substitution metrics

The carbon price should be imposed on all Kyoto gases represented in the model. 100 yr Global Warming Potentials (GWPs) should be used to convert the carbon price to greenhouse gases prices for non-CO₂ greenhouse gases. Models should use their default assumption of 100-year GWPs (AR4, AR5), and document this assumption in their submission of scenario data.

Scenarios

There are four types of scenarios we aim to run. More details on individual scenarios are given in ECEMF. (2022). Model Comparison Protocol (2.1). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6782403>

References

Koch, Johannes, and Marian Leimbach. 2022. 'Update of Ssp GDP Projections: Capturing Recent Changes in National Accounting, PPP Conversion and Covid 19 Impacts'. SSRN Scholarly Paper. Rochester, NY. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4011838>.

Annex 1 – Scenario details. For models with foresight or intertemporal optimization, this may require fixing the scenario values to the baseline values up to 2020 to keep coherence across the scenarios, if directly turning off the anticipation is not possible.

Baseline scenario and current policy

It is strongly recommended that global modelling teams (but not necessarily national modelling teams) harmonize their GDP and population assumptions in the baseline to the updated SSP2 marker scenario (Koch and Leimbach 2022) for non-EU regions and to the EU GDP/pop projections for EU Member States, including the effects of COVID-19. Baseline harmonization is, however, not required to keep the barrier for participation as low as possible. If modelling teams choose to harmonize population and GDP trajectories in the baseline, they may use their preferred approach for matching the SSP2 population and GDP scenarios on the level of their native model regions. Modelling teams should also use their default method of adapting external PPP GDP projections in their modelling framework.

DIAG-BASE

The ‘no-climate-policy baseline’ (DIAG-Base, lower priority) is not expected to match the observed greenhouse gas emissions until today, since the observed quantities are already affected by current climate policies or the expectations thereof in some regions.

DIAG-NPI

We use a current-policy baseline (DIAG-NPI, implemented policies) to bring the historic model results closer to real world values for this diagnostic exercise.

To clarify, DIAG-NPI is supposed to only include currently implemented policies, but not targets that are not yet translated into policies. Examples are:

- ESR targets for 2030 that are not yet translated into concrete policies should not be included
- (current) ETS cap for 2020-2030 can/should be included
- A coal phaseout in Germany by 2038 can be included, as there concrete phaseout of the different plants is written in law

Pure carbon pricing/GHG target scenarios

DIAG-C80-gr5 / DIAG-C0to80-gr5 / DIAG-C400-lin

The carbon price scenarios should be imposed globally, across all sectors (ETS and non-ETS). The price level in the name refers to the CO₂ price in 2040. All price levels in USD 2010 per ton CO₂-eq, see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Carbon price paths in the prescribed carbon price diagnostic scenarios

DIAG-NZero

The net-zero scenario imposes a global peak budget constraint (1100 Gt CO₂ from 2011 to peaking year) and EU reaching net zero by 2050 (for concrete 2050 targets for models that do not cover all GHG and/or LULUCF, see Emission sources). The global carbon budget should be imposed in a way that allows full ‘where and what’ flexibility, leading to a globally uniform carbon price across regions and sectors.

The scenario should be fixed to **DIAG-NPI** results until 2020 in order to reproduce historic data. After 2020, there should be full flexibility of emissions reductions leading to a globally harmonized carbon price across all regions (except for the EU regions with their own 2050 GHG neutrality target) and sectors. This represents an idealized policy implementation that is used as a benchmark in most studies.

Models should use their default methodology to implement a carbon budget in their model, including their standard treatment of when flexibility. The socio-economic assumptions used in models should be the same as in **DIAG-NPI/DIAG-Base** scenarios.

If model runs are not feasible, models should enforce the maximum feasible reduction.

Technology Constraint scenarios

These follow the **DIAG-C400-lin** protocol, with additional technology constraints after 2020. Results intend to highlight changes in mitigation pathways, marginal technologies, and carbon price (or emission shadow price). Details for each scenario are shown in Annex 1, Table 1.

LimBio

Test sensitivity to limited biomass (as opposed to default model assumption) for modern bioenergy, particularly in the transport and power sectors. Limit is applied both globally (primary energy) and for the EU specifically (Secondary Energy, see Table 1). The EU constraint is applied on total modern bioenergy consumption and includes potential imports. No constraints on “traditional biomass” use are applied.

LimCCS

Test sensitivity of the results on the availability CCS, including carbon dioxide removal from BECCS and DAC. Limit is applied both globally, and for the EU specifically. (see Table 1).

LimNuclear

Test sensitivity of the power sector to limited nuclear capacity. Scenario assumes no new nuclear capacity (except for those currently under construction). Limit is applied globally.

Paradigm Shift scenarios

All the below scenarios are in combination with the **DIAG-C400-lin** CO₂ price path and implemented mainly for the European regions (can also be implemented for the other regions if easier to do, but not necessary if complicated).

High VRE

Test if the model represents well the fact that through flexibility options/storage/grid, power sectors can work well with very high VRE shares without electricity costs increasing strongly.

High electrification

Test if the model represents well the electrification options in all demand sectors and accordingly reduces demand for other energy carriers if it has large amounts of comparatively cheap electricity available.

High H2

Test if the model represents well the ways in which H2 can be used throughout the energy system.

ResidualFossil

Test if there are some dynamics forcing fossil fuel use, which could be covered in normal runs by using CCS.

HighEff

Test the effect of reducing energy demand due to increasing efficiency. This includes both technological efficiency, but also structural changes (lifestyle change, etc.).

Issues and Code Sharing

Tracking Model Issues

The models differ from each other in many ways. It is important to use an issue tracker to ease communication on, for example, different or missing variables, regional aggregation and different assumptions in policies, or mere problems with uploads and runs. The ECEMF modelling teams currently use a spreadsheet to list issues, but this only allows for weak interaction. Alternatives could include an issue tracker on Github, which provides for a good potential interaction with versioned material, such as this protocol but has a steep learning curve, a shared document or a forum post on <http://community.ecemf.eu>. The appropriate tool will be chosen once it becomes necessary to move beyond the current solution.

Code sharing

Code for the diagnostics is shared via the ECEMF Github repository:
<https://github.com/ecemf>.

At the time of writing, a [script for model comparison](#) is available, and more scripts, tools and utilities will be made available over time.

Access to the Scenario Explorer

The process for obtaining access to the ECEMF scenario explorer is as follows:

1. Create an account at <http://manager.ece.iiasa.ac.at>
2. Contact the database administrator or project leader to be given access to a project-specific Scenario Explorer instance (info@ecemf.eu)
3. Prepare your data in the IAMC data format using the nomenclature (list of variables and regions) for the specific project
4. Log into the Scenario Explorer for the project, go to “Uploads” and follow the instructions
5. Check your emails to see if the scenario processing and validation worked as expected

There are a few tutorials at <http://software.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ixmp-server/tutorials.html> for working with the Scenario Explorer.

Support and Help

Learning materials, reading lists and papers, tutorial videos and software tools are available on the ECEMF website (<https://www.ecemf.eu/learn/>) to help support new modelling teams join the model comparison exercise.

Protocol Update Procedure

Versioning

Each version of the protocol is assigned a version number based on concept of semantic versioning. The version number consists of MAJOR and MINOR integers separated by a period: MAJOR.MINOR. For example, v15.2, v3.11 and v0.5 are all valid version numbers.

The significance of increments to the version number as follows. The MINOR number is incremented when a non-breaking change is made to the protocol. For example, a clarifying change is made to a prio2 scenario description, or a typo is corrected. Other examples include:

- A scenario is removed from the protocol

The MAJOR number is incremented when a breaking-change is made to the protocol which requires all modelling teams to re-run at least one scenario. This may happen when:

- A new scenario is added to the protocol
- A global assumption (such as exchange rate) found in one or more scenarios is changed

Process for Updating the Protocol

The Model Comparison Protocol is managed centrally by Task 1.1 in the ECEMF project. Within the ECEMF project, the protocol is discussed at regular meetings (within Work Package 1), with the owners of the models listed in Annex 3 – Core models participating in ECEMF.

Generally, researchers make suggestions for a new scenario with a justification for how it would add new information about the behaviour of the model. Researchers then work together to determine an implementation that works across as many models as possible.

Publication of the Protocol

Each version of this Protocol document is archived by the Document Manager on Zenodo, and the latest version can be found under DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6782373](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6782373). The link to the Protocol is made from the ECEMF website: <https://www.ecemf.eu/publications/>

The citation for v2.1 is:

ECEMF. (2022). Model Comparison Protocol (2.1). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6782403>

References

Koch, Johannes, and Marian Leimbach. 2022. 'Update of Ssp GDP Projections: Capturing Recent Changes in National Accounting, PPP Conversion and Covid 19 Impacts'. SSRN Scholarly Paper. Rochester, NY. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4011838>.

Annex 1 – Scenario details

Table 1 Overview of ECEMF Diagnostic scenarios.

	Name	Prio	Description	First year with deviation from DIAG-NPI
1a	DIAG-Base	2	No policies	-
1b	DIAG-NPI	1	National Policies Implemented – try to recreate the actual 2020 values. If needed, this can include currently implemented policies (but not targets that are not supported by policies, such as the ESR targets for 2030 if they are not yet translated into national measures)	-
2	DIAG-C80-gr5	1	For $t < 2025$: Fix scenario to DIAG-NPI For t in $[2025, 2100]$: $\text{Tax}(t) = 80 \text{ USD} * 1.05^{(t-2040)}$ (USD 80 reached in 2040)	2023/2025
3	DIAG-C0to80-gr5	1	For $t < 2040$: Fix scenario to DIAG- NPI For t in $[2040, 2100]$: $\text{Tax}(t) = 80 \text{ USD} * 1.05^{(t-2040)}$	2040
4	DIAG-C400-lin	1	For $t < 2025$: Fix scenario to DIAG- NPI For t in $[2025, 2100]$: $\text{Tax}(t) = 130 \text{ USD} + 18 \text{ USD} * (t-2025)$; (USD 400 reached in 2040, 580 in 2050)	2023/2025
5	DIAG-NZero	1	See “Emission Sources” above for how to treat different emission sources Globally implement a 1100 CO ₂ peak Budget from 2011-peaking time. Ideally this constraint is met via CO ₂ prices; otherwise, it is also allowed to implement other policies & measures, The main intention of this scenarios is to see a net Zero pathway. How the model is parameterized to reach that is less important.	2023/2025

			<p>Net-zero GHG emissions in 2050 in EU. See “Regional Scale” above for accepted regional aggregation</p> <p>If net zero cannot be reached in any region, apply the max feasible reduction</p>	
6	DIAG-C400-lin-LimBio	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Global primary modern bioenergy supply (from any primary resource) is limited to 100EJ.</p> <p>Maximum biomass use in the EU is limited to 7 EJ (Secondary energy level) and 10 EJ (primary energy level).</p>	2023/2025
7	DIAG-C400-lin-LimCCS	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Global application of Carbon Capture and Storage (including DACCS and BECCS) is limited to a maximum of 2GtCO₂/yr.</p> <p>Max CCS use in the EU28 is limited to 250 Mt CO₂/yr</p>	2023/2025
8	DIAG-C400-lin-LimNuclear	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Regional use of Nuclear power is limited to today’s levels, and no new construction are allowed (except capacity already under construction)</p>	2023/2025
9	DIAG-C400-lin-HighVRE (tests VRE integration and potentials)	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Preferred implementation: provide cheap VRE: reduce investment costs such that direct LCOE for wind and solar PV are ~10€/MWh</p> <p>Alternative implementations, depending on model type: require a VRE share of >75% in optimizing models make nuclear, CCS power plants and biomass power plants extremely expensive (simulation models)</p>	2023/2025

10	DIAG-C400-lin-HighElectrification (tests mostly the demand side of IAMs)	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Preferred implementation: provide cheap (emission-free) electricity to the demand sectors, at ~30€/MWh (the 30€ already includes costs to make electricity “firm”, ie storage costs etc, but it does not include transmission & distribution costs, taxes and sales markups)</p> <p>Alternative implementations, depending on model type: require electricity shares >70% in TFC (when excluding bunkers and industry feedstocks)</p>	2023/2025
11	DIAG-C400-lin-HighH2 (tests mostly the demand side of IAMs)	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Preferred implementation: provide cheap emission-free hydrogen to the demand sectors, at around ~45€/MWh (~1.5€/kg). (price does not include transmission & distribution costs, taxes and sales markups)</p> <p>Alternative implementations, depending on model type: require an H2 share in TFC of >50% or as close to 50% as possible</p>	2023/2025
12	DIAG-C400-lin-ResidualFossil	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Limit residual fossil use (including feedstocks) in 2050 <5% of 2015 value</p> <p>Alternative implementations, depending on model type: upper limit on residual fuel use make coal/oil/gas much more expensive strongly limit CCS</p>	2023/2025
13	DIAG-C400-lin-HighEff	2	<p>Emission prices follow DIAG-C400-lin</p> <p>Apply high efficiency and Lifestyle change options available in the models, including”</p>	2023/2025

			<p>Use optimistic assumptions for conversion technology and final energy use efficiency</p> <p>Transition to high efficiency technologies (i.e. heat pumps, electric vehicles)</p> <p>Reduce sectoral final energy demand by lowering activity (i.e. lifestyle change)</p> <p>Reduce sectoral final energy demand via technology (i.e. Increased insulation)</p> <p>Reduce sectoral final energy demand via changing structure (i.e. mode shifting in transport)</p>	
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Annex 2 – Currency conversions

Table 2 Currency conversions (*first US CPI, then exchange rates)

	USD -> USD	EUR -> EUR	USD -> EUR*
2005 -> 2005	1.00	1.00	0.80
2005 -> 2010	1.12	1.10	0.84
2005 -> 2015	1.21	1.18	1.09
2005 -> 2020	1.33	1.24	1.17
2010 -> 2010	1.00	1.00	0.75
2010 -> 2015	1.08	1.08	0.97
2010 -> 2020	1.19	1.13	1.04
2015 -> 2015	1.00	1.00	0.90
2015 -> 2020	1.10	1.05	0.96
2020 -> 2020	1.00	1.00	0.88

Annex 3 – Core models participating in ECEMF

IMAGE	IMAGE is an IAM framework developed to describe the relationships between humans and natural systems and the impacts of these relationships on the provision of ecosystem services to sustain human development. The energy module of IMAGE, TIMER, is a recursive dynamic (i.e., no-foresight) energy system model representing the global energy system, disaggregated across 26 global regions, with projections till 2100. Primary energy carriers can be converted to secondary and final energy carriers (solids, liquids, electricity, hydrogen, heat) to provide energy services for different end-use sectors (heavy industry, transport, residential, services, chemicals and other). The model projects future (useful) energy demand for each end-use sector (industry, transport, residential, commercial, other) based on relationships between energy services and activity, the latter of which is related to economic growth. For each demand sector, secondary energy carriers (including solid and liquid biofuels) compete based on relative costs with each other to meet the useful energy demand. The energy system representation of the IMAGE model does include demand elasticity with carbon prices via investments in efficiency and reduction of demand.
OSEMBE	The Open-Source electricity Model Base for Europe (OSEMBE) is a long-term techno-economic energy investment optimization model for the power sector of the EU, the United Kingdom, Switzerland, and Norway. It is based on the Open-Source energy Modelling SYStem (OSEMOSYS) (Howells et al. 2011). With an annual temporal resolution from 2015 to 2050 and a comprehensive set of technologies, it allows the modelling of detailed decarbonization scenarios for the European power sector. The open-source nature of the model and modelling framework facilitate collaboration and expansion of the model.
PROMETHEUS	PROMETHEUS is a comprehensive global energy system simulation model focusing on technology uptake analysis, energy price projections, and assessment of energy and climate policies. It captures the complex interactions between energy demand and supply and price formation at regional and global level and provides detailed projections of fuel mix in energy consumption, electricity production mix by technology, carbon emissions, energy prices and investment for the 10 world regions represented in the model. PROMETHEUS can provide medium- and long-term energy system projections up to 2050, in both the demand and the supply sides, under different policy and technology scenarios. About 70 technology types are included in the model, related to energy supply (thermal power plants, renewable energy sources, hydrogen production facilities) and end-uses in transport (private cars, buses, trucks, planes), buildings, and industries.
REMIND	The energy-economy-climate model REMIND is a Ramsey-type general equilibrium growth model of the macro-economy in which inter-temporal global welfare is maximized, with a technology-rich representation of the energy system and full sectoral coverage. REMIND accounts for relevant path-dependencies, such as the build-up of long-lived capital stocks, as well as learning-by-doing effects and inertias in the up-scaling of innovative technologies. REMIND operates in time-steps of five years for

	the period from 2005 to 2060, and ten years for the rest of the century. Europe is represented by nine sub-regions, with 13 other regions covering the entire world.
TIAM-ECN	TIAM-ECN is a global technology-rich linear optimization model that identifies cost-minimal energy system scenarios under a set of exogenous constraints. It is a global IAM based on the TIMES model generator and developed and maintained at TNO Energy Transition. TIAM-ECN encompasses energy use in all main sectors and its input database includes hundreds of processes simulating energy conversion from resource extraction to end-use. In the current version of TIAM-ECN the world is broken down into 36 separate geographical entities. TIAM-ECN has been employed to provide long-term projections for many different technologies, including in transport, industry, power generation and the residential & commercial sector, and has been used to investigate stringent climate-change mitigation efforts, international burden sharing and technology diffusion.
WITCH	WITCH consists of a dynamic global model that integrates in a unified framework the most important elements of climate change. The economy is modelled through an inter-temporal optimal growth model which captures the long-term economic growth dynamics. A compact representation of the energy sector is fully integrated (hard linked) with the rest of the economy so that energy investments and resources are chosen optimally, together with the other macroeconomic variables. Land use mitigation options are available through a soft link with a land use and forestry model (GLOBIOM). WITCH represents the world in a set of representative and flexibly defined native regions (or coalitions of regions), and for this paper this set has been extended to 34 regions in total including 10 large EU member states.
MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM	The IIASA Integrated Assessment Modeling (IAM) framework, also referred to as MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM, has two important components, i.e., the energy model MESSAGEix and the land use model GLOBIOM. The MESSAGEix framework (Huppmann et al., 2019) is an open-source energy systems optimization modelling environment and helps to explore cost-optimal energy and emissions policies in long-term planning. MESSAGEix includes a macro-economic (MACRO) module, which provides demand response to energy prices using a stylized computable general equilibrium model. The model is based on 5-year time steps from 2020 to 2060, and 10-year time steps between 2060-2100. GLOBIOM provides MESSAGEix with information on land use and its implications, including the availability and cost of bioenergy, and availability and cost of emission mitigation in the AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use) sector.
Sector-Coupled EURO-Calliope	An energy system optimization model, it optimizes capacity expansion and system operation at hourly resolution over a full year of weather data. It includes 35 countries, further disaggregated into 98 sub-national regions, and it considers all energy sectors: power, heat, transport, and industry. Not looking at capacity deployment through time, Sector-Coupled Euro-Calliope identifies the end-state least-cost system configurations for 2030 and 2050 that are coherent with a given policy scenario or emissions reduction target.
MEESA	Linear optimization model of the energy sector designed for the assessment of long-term climate and energy strategies in EU. Given a data of demands for electricity, district heat and hydrogen, the model assures sufficient supply to demand, utilizing the technologies and resources considered. The model operates annually or in 5-years steps for 2020-2050 period, with differentiation of demand for electricity and district heat according to seasons, types of days (different demand and weather conditions) and time of day. About 50 different types of technologies are defined in the model, including existing and new conventional thermal units, RES, energy storage, electrolyzers, and DSR.